

Co_xFe_{3-x}O₄ Nanocubes with High r₂ Relaxivity and Specific Absorption Rate for Theranostic Applications: Effect of Cobalt Content and Particle Size

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Abstract:

We report a facile synthesis of cube-shaped Co_xFe_{3-x}O₄ nanocrystals (NCs), which could be finely tuned in terms of NC size (from 15 to 27 nm) and cobalt stoichiometry (from 0.3 to 0.7). These particles exhibited high specific absorption rate (SAR) values, relevant for magnetic hyperthermia, and high relaxivity values, significant for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) applications. The peculiarities of these NCs is that, already at low frequencies (such as 105 kHz, a working frequency used on human patients), they display SAR values that are three times as large as those of iron oxides nanocubes of comparable sizes (and which were already considered outstanding). The highest SAR value recorded on the NCs reported here ($915 \pm 10 \text{ Wg}^{-1}_{(\text{Co+Fe})}$ at 105 kHz and 32 kAm^{-1}) refers to particles with cube shape, 20 ± 2 nm edge size and Co stoichiometry equal to 0.6 to 0.7. The highest r₂ value ($958 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) was instead recorded on nanocubes with Co stoichiometry equal to 0.5/0.6 and size of 20 ± 2 nm. Remarkably, only at this specific size and Co stoichiometry, the NCs were not perfect cubes but had a concave-cubic shape, which might account for the higher r₂ values recorded. NCs reported here, with optimized SAR and r₂ values, are promising tools for theranostic applications.

Introduction

When magnetic nanocrystals (NCs) are exposed to alternating magnetic fields, they are able to convert the electromagnetic energy into thermal energy. In doing so, the particles act as nanometric heating hubs that can be used for tumor ablation.¹ The same magnetic NCs can act as T₂-weighted image contrast agents capable of perturbing the relaxation time of water protons and improving the sensitivity of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI),²⁻⁵ a non-invasive medical imaging technique.⁴ Non-hydrolytic colloidal syntheses have uncovered the possibility to finely control size, composition and shape⁶⁻⁸ of the magnetic NCs, such that their magnetic properties can be optimized both for hyperthermia and for MRI applications.⁹⁻¹¹ The relevant parameters that regulate the heating ability and the relaxivity of the NCs, and which can be tuned in principle by chemical synthesis, are the saturation magnetization (M_s), the remnant magnetization (M_r), the susceptibility (X), the coercivity (H_c) and the surface anisotropy (K_s).^{6, 8, 12-20} Iron oxide NCs are among the most promising materials for clinical applications, given their biocompatibility and their proven *in vivo* biodegradability.^{3, 21, 22} Unfortunately, the roughly spherical shaped iron oxide NPs that are currently approved by FDA for medical applications²³ are plagued by low values of M_s (due to large surface spin disorder)²⁴ which reduce their performance in both hyperthermia and MRI applications. Recently, it was found that monodisperse iron oxide NCs with cubic shapes (nanocubes) have M_s values that are closer to that of bulk magnetite (90 emu/g), a peculiarity that has been ascribed to a combination of beneficial effects in these particles, such as lower surface spin disorder, higher crystallinity and higher magnetic moments.^{6, 16, 25, 26}

Compositional tuning^{11, 27-31} has been also reported as an alternative and effective strategy to tailor the magnetic properties of iron oxide NCs.^{10, 11, 32-37} Particles of various spinel ferrites can now be routinely prepared by partial or complete replacement of the Fe²⁺ ions in magnetite (Fe₃O₄) NCs with other divalent transition metal ions (Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Mn²⁺).^{11, 31, 38} Among the various spinel ferrites, CoFe₂O₄ stands out as particularly appealing material: despite its bulk M_s (80 emu/g) being lower than that of Fe₃O₄ (89 emu/g), this material is characterized by a high intrinsic magnetocrystalline anisotropy (K), of nearly 2×10^5 Jm⁻³. This value is almost one order of magnitude higher than that of Fe₃O₄ and it is responsible for the large coercivity of CoFe₂O₄.³⁹ In CoFe₂O₄ NCs, such large coercivity values should provide hysteresis loops that are larger than those of other spinel ferrite NCs of similar size, and would translate into a higher heat dissipation.⁴⁰

There is indeed a strong interest in preparing and testing CoFe_2O_4 NCs with different sizes, shapes and cobalt stoichiometry for hyperthermia applications. One of the few works published to date on SAR values of spherical and faceted CoFe_2O_4 NCs of different sizes (6 – 25 nm) is that of Joshi *et al.*⁴¹ The authors attributed the generally observed trend of higher SAR values in larger particles to the increase of M_s with size,⁴¹ and then attempted to compare faceted CoFe_2O_4 of 12 nm size to 10 nm spherical nanoparticles. They recorded lower SAR values and lower M_s values on the faceted particles, most likely due to the poorer morphology control and to a wider polydispersity in this latter case. Besides hyperthermia, CoFe_2O_4 NCs have also been tested as T_2 -weighted image contrast agents.^{16, 41-46} The transverse relaxivity (r_2) of CoFe_2O_4 NCs of different sizes (from 6 to 25 nm) was studied by Joshi *et al.*,^{10, 41} who likewise ascribed the increase in r_2 relaxivity with particle size to the corresponding increase in M_s .⁴¹ Recently, Georgiadou *et al.* studied the effect of hydrodynamic size on the r_2 relaxivity of 10 nm CoFe_2O_4 NCs⁴⁷ and recorded a high r_2 relaxivity value of $553 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ at an applied magnetic field of 11.7 T.

The effect of shape and composition of cobalt ferrite NCs on their thermal and MRI performance is comparatively less explored. Song *et al.* synthesized CoFe_2O_4 nanocubes of 9 nm in size using 5 nm size CoFe_2O_4 spherical seeds in a thermal decomposition method,⁴⁸ while, more recently, Sun and co-workers prepared cobalt substituted magnetite NCs with tunable cobalt content and size by one-pot synthesis approach,⁴⁹ and later were able to synthesize the same types of particles in the cubic shape.³⁰ Unfortunately, the magnetic properties of the resulting particles were poorer than those of previously synthesized octahedral particles with similar size (35 nm) and composition ($\text{Co}_{0.6}\text{Fe}_{2.4}\text{O}_4$).³⁰ In this case, the defects present in the pristine sample were removed only upon annealing at 300°C under O_2 atmosphere.

Regardless of these previous investigations on CoFe_2O_4 NCs (including others not mentioned above),^{42, 50} there is to date no synthetic pathway to cobalt ferrite NCs which allowed tuning the particle size for a given composition and, *vice versa*, tuning the composition for a given particle size in the range useful for magnetic hyperthermia. In this work, we report a synthesis protocol of $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes, by means of thermal decomposition, which enables the control of both size and cobalt stoichiometry in the NCs. This was achieved by carefully tuning the synthetic parameters, specifically: i) molar ratio of cobalt to iron precursors and ii) molar ratio of surfactant to total metal (Co + Fe) precursors; iii) heating rate; iv) composition of the solvent mixture. The as synthesized,

surfactant coated hydrophobic $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes, in spite of their strong magnetic dipolar interactions, could be successfully transferred into water by using an amphiphilic polymer coating,^{51, 52} allowing their further SAR and MRI characterization in aqueous solution. Remarkably, in comparison to iron oxide nanocubes these particles exhibited much higher SAR values already at low frequencies, a performance that is unmatched by any magnetic NC system reported to date. The highest SAR values were recorded on $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes of 18-20 nm in cube edge and with Co stoichiometry ranging from 0.5 to 0.7. Notably, only the sample of nanocubes of 18-20 nm in size and Co stoichiometry around 0.5 to 0.6 had a slightly concave shape and exhibited at the same time the highest r_2 relaxivity value and the highest SAR value, and therefore represents in our view a suitable candidate for combined local heat-mediated drug delivery and MRI imaging.

Experimental Section

Materials. Iron (III) acetylacetonate (99%) and decanoic acid (99%) were purchased from Acros. Cobalt (II) acetylacetonate (99%), Poly maleic anhydride 1 – octadecene (PMAO), sucrose, Agarose, dibenzylether, acetone, chloroform and isopropanol were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Squalane (98%) was purchased from Alfa Aesar. Milli-Q water filtered through 0.22 μm pore size hydrophilic filters with resistivity of 18.2 $\text{M}\Omega\text{-cm}$ from Millipore. All solvents were of analytical grade and were used as received.

Synthesis of $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes. $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes were synthesized by thermal decomposition following a previously developed procedure with suitable modifications.⁶ We report, in the following, the detailed procedure for the synthesis of particles of 20 nm in size and with Co stoichiometry of 0.5. Syntheses conditions for other sizes and compositions are summarized in the Table S1 of the supporting information (SI). The synthesis and purification of the particles consisted of the following steps: i) in a three-neck flask connected to a standard Schlenk line, 0.5 mmoles (129 mg) of $\text{Co}(\text{acac})_2$, 1 mmole (353 mg) of $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ and 6 mmoles (1033 mg) of decanoic acid were dissolved in a mixture of 7 mL squalane and 18 mL benzyl ether; ii) the resulting deep red solution was degassed at 65°C for 2 h under reduced pressure of 50 mTorr; iii) under N_2 flow, the temperature of the mixture was increased to 200°C at the rate of 5 °C/min and was then kept at 200 °C for 2 h; iv) the reaction temperature was increased to 305 °C at the rate of 7.5°C/min, and then the mixture was kept at reflux for 1 h; v) the flask was cooled down to room temperature under inert

atmosphere. The black colloidal solution was washed 3 times with excess amount of isopropanol (10 mL) and acetone (30 mL) mixture and centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 10min. The final particles were dispersed in chloroform (8 mL) for further measurements.

Phase transfer of the $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes in water with PMAO. The as-synthesized, hydrophobic $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes were transferred to water by using Poly maleic anhydride 1-octadecene (PMAO) polymer, following a protocol previously developed by our group with suitable modifications.^{51, 52} Initially, 20 nm size nanocubes (2 mL with Co and Fe concentrations of 1 and 5 mg/mL) were diluted with an excess amount of chloroform (200 mL) and sonicated for 10 min. A specific amount of PMAO polymer solution in chloroform (137 mM, concentration referred to the monomer units) was added by fixing 500 molecules of monomer unit for each nm^2 of NC surface and the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure (fixed at 460 mbar) until complete solvent evaporation occurred. The sample (in a form of flakes) was then soaked in 20 mL of borate buffer and was left shaking overnight at 65°C. The well dispersed sample was concentrated by using centrifugal filters (Amicon ultra, with 100 kDa in molecular weight cut off). The sample volume was reduced to nearly 2 mL after repeated centrifugation steps at room temperature (RT) at 1500 rpm for 10 min per each cycle. Subsequently the sample was loaded on top of a sucrose gradient (2mL of 20%, 4mL of 40% and 3 mL of 60% in a ultra-centrifugal tube) and centrifuged at 30,000 rpm for 60 min. Excess polymer (visible under ultraviolet (UV) lamp) from the top of sucrose gradient at 20% sucrose was removed by syringe aspiration and the nanocubes were usually found in the fraction at 40% to 60% of the sucrose gradient. The collected sample was washed further with borate buffer solution (pH 9) for several times to remove the excess of sucrose and finally it was dispersed in buffer solution for better solubility.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Diluted solutions of nanocubes were dropped onto carbon coated 300 mesh copper grids and the solvent was allowed to evaporate at room temperature. Bright field TEM images were acquired using a JEOL JEM 1011 microscope equipped with a thermionic gun operating at an accelerating voltage of 100 kV. The elemental distribution within the NCs was determined by energy-filtered TEM (EFTEM), carried out on a JEOL JEM-2200FS TEM, equipped with an in-column imaging filter (Ω -type) and a CEOS C_s -corrector for the objective lens. EFTEM elemental maps were obtained via the three-windows method on the Fe L_{23} (40 eV slit width), Co L_{23} (30 eV slit width), O K (30 eV slit width) and C K (20 eV slit width) core-loss edges. Elemental quantification in

the samples was determined via Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) analysis performed on the same instrument in high angle annular dark field scanning TEM (HAADF-STEM) mode with a Bruker Quantax 400 system with a 60 mm² XFlash 6T silicon drift detector (SDD), using the Cliff-Lorimer method. For EFTEM analyses, the sample suspensions were drop-cast onto ultrathin carbon/holey carbon-coated Cu grids.

X-ray diffraction (XRD). XRD patterns were recorded on a Rigaku SmartLab diffractometer operating at 9 kW. The X-ray source is operated at 40 kV and 150 mA. The diffractometer was equipped with a Cu source and a Göbel mirror to obtain a parallel beam as well as to suppress Cu K_β radiation (1.392Å). 2-theta/omega scan geometry was used to acquire the data. The samples were prepared by drop casting concentrated NC solutions onto a zero background silicon substrate. The PDXL software of Rigaku was used for phase identification.

Elemental analysis. Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) analysis was performed on an iCAP 6000 spectrometer (ThermoScientific) to quantify the cobalt and iron concentration. 25 μL samples were digested in 2.5 mL of aqua regia (HCl:HNO₃ is 3:1 (v/v)) and diluted with 25 mL of milliQ water prior to the measurement. The detailed ICP analysis and estimation of Co content are given in the SI.

Dynamic light scattering (DLS). The hydrodynamic size was estimated by using dynamic light scattering (DLS) from Malvern Instruments Zetasizer nano. The scattered intensity was collected at 173° back scattered geometry with 632 nm laser source. For each sample 3 measurements were taken with 10 acquisitions each.

Magnetic characterization. Magnetic measurements were performed on a MPMS superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) from Quantum Design Inc. Hysteresis curves were measured within the magnetic field of ±70 kOe at 5 K and 298 K respectively. Temperature dependent magnetization studies, zero field cooled (ZFC) and field cooled (FC) curves were recorded under a magnetic field of 50 Oe. In a ZFC protocol, the sample was cooled from room temperature to 5 K without any magnetic field and the magnetization was measured during heating from 5 to 400 K at 2 K/min under the magnetic field of 50 Oe. In a FC protocol, the same sample was cooled down to 5 K under the 50 Oe magnetic field and the magnetization was recorded during heating mode from 5 to 400 K under same heating rate.

Relaxivity measurements. The transverse relaxation times (T_2) were measured using a Minispec spectrometer (Bruker, Germany) mq 20 (0.5 T), mq 40 (1 T) and mq 60 (1.5 T). The T_2 relaxation time was measured using a Carr–Purcell Meiboom Gill (CPMG) spin–echo pulse sequence with 200 data points with inter echo time of 0.5 ms. The relaxivity r_2 was determined from the slope of the following equation:

$$\frac{1}{T_{2(Obs.)}} = \frac{1}{T_{2(H_2O)}} + r_2 C_{Fe+Co} \quad (1)$$

where, C_{Fe+Co} is the concentration of both Fe +Co ions. The values were reproducible within 5% deviation.

Specific absorption rate (SAR). A commercially available DM100 Series (nanoscale Biomagnetics) was used to evaluate the SAR values under quasi adiabatic conditions. The cobalt ferrite nanocubes were exposed to an alternating magnetic field (from 12 up to 32 kA/m) at 3 different frequencies of 105, 220 and 300 kHz. All measurements were performed on 300 μ L of sample in water (at a Fe concentration of 5 g/L) and SAR were normalized by using the sum of cobalt and iron concentration as determined by elemental analysis (g/L). SAR values were calculated according to the following equation:

$$SAR (W/g) = \frac{C}{m} \cdot \frac{dT}{dt} \quad (2)$$

where C is the specific heat capacity of water (4185 $JL^{-1}K^{-1}$) per unit volume and m is the concentration (g/L of Co+Fe) of magnetic material in solution. Temperature data were collected within the first 60 seconds typical examples of T vs. t curves are reported in the supporting (Figure S15). Each data point is given as the mean of at least three independent measurements.

Results and Discussion

Synthesis of nanocubes of tunable Co stoichiometry and edge size. An initial series of syntheses was performed in which the amount of cobalt precursor (here $Co(acac)_2$) added to the reaction flask was systematically varied from 0.11 to 0.87 mmoles, while keeping the amounts of all other chemicals fixed (1 mmol of $Fe(acac)_2$, 18 mL of benzyl ether, 7 mL of squalene, and 6 mmoles of decanoic acid) and by applying a well-defined heating ramp, as detailed in the experimental part. The initial experimental parameters were set following conditions, previously developed by our group, that were known to deliver nanocubes of iron oxide of 18-20 nm in cube-edge,⁶ as it had been already found by us that iron oxide

nanocubes at this size range had maximized SAR values. The $\text{Co}(\text{acac})_2/\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ ratio of Co to Fe precursors used in the synthesis, defined as $\text{mmoles}_{\text{Co}}/\text{mmoles}_{\text{Fe}}$, is henceforth abbreviated as “Co/Fe feed ratio”. Depending on the Co/Fe feed ratio (bottom axis in the plot of Figure 1), the cobalt stoichiometry (x) in the final $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes (left axis in the plot of Figure 1) could be tuned from 0.1 to 1, as determined by elemental analysis (Figure 1, black dots). There was a roughly linear dependence of the Co stoichiometry in the nanocubes on the $\text{Co}(\text{acac})_2/\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ feed ratio. The Co/Fe ratio in the NCs was instead calculated as $x/(3-x)$, since the formula for cobalt ferrite is $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$. This is reported on the right axis of Figure 1. The Co/Fe ratio found in the NCs was always lower than the initial Co/Fe feed ratio, meaning that a significant fraction of Co species had remained in solution. These findings are similar to those of Yu *et al.*,⁴⁹ who synthesized $\text{Co}_{0.6}\text{Fe}_{2.4}\text{O}_4$ NCs (that is, with a Co/Fe ratio equal to 0.25), starting from a Co/Fe feed equal to 0.5 (in their case, the surfactants used were oleic acid and oleylamine). In our syntheses, the variation in the amount of Co precursor affected also the size of the particles, which stayed at 18 nm when working at a Co/Fe feed ratio below 0.5, but then gradually increases from 18 nm up to 27 nm for a Co/Fe feed ratio larger than 0.5 and up to 0.9. Since all the other parameters remained fixed (including the total amount of surfactants) we hypothesized that the main effect of adding more Co precursor in the syntheses is that, on average, less surfactant (decanoic acid) is available per particle to regulate the growth, hence the particles grow bigger. One important parameter that we decided to track was therefore the mole ratio of surfactant (decanoic acid) to total metal precursors [$\text{Co}(\text{acac})_2 + \text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$], henceforth referred to as “*surfactant/(total metal)*”. In this first series of experiments, this ratio was uniquely dictated by the amount of Co precursor, according to the formula: $\text{surfactant}/(\text{total metal}) = 6/(\text{mmoles}_{\text{Fe}} + \text{mmoles}_{\text{Co}}) = 6/(1 + \text{mmoles}_{\text{Co}})$ and is reported in the upper axis of Figure 1.

These initial experiments, as displayed in Figure 1, suggest that the Co stoichiometry is regulated by the Co/Fe feed ratio, while the size of the particles is regulated in part by the surfactant to metal precursor ratio. To prove our hypothesis, in a second series of experiments, indicated by the three gray data points under the shadowed area of Figure 1, we worked at Co/Fe ratios around 0.65 to 0.85, in order to synthesize cobalt ferrite NCs at high Co content, but this time we slightly lowered the moles of Fe and Co precursors added, such that the *surfactant/(total metal)* ratio stayed around 4 (for these synthesis the decanoic acid was fixed at 6 mmol). As expected, in these experiments, the final sizes of the particles were

indeed around 20 nm, which supports our initial hypothesis. Additional details on the synthesis conditions are reported in the Table S1 of the SI, while Figure 2 reports representative TEM images of six out of the ten samples of $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes plotted in Figure 1. The corresponding size distribution plots are given in Fig. S2. The samples were chosen to highlight the tunability in the Co stoichiometry, while at the same time keeping the size of the particles around 20 nm. We also ran syntheses in which the Surfactant/(total metal) ratio was varied (from 4 to 5.3 to 6), this time by increasing the amount of surfactant. In these experiments, the shape of the particles departed from cubic at ratio 4 and above, and was definitely closer to spherical at ratio 5.3 and 6.6 (representative TEM images and details of these syntheses are reported in Figure S1 of the SI).

Figure 1. Black points: series of syntheses of cobalt ferrite nanocubes in which the amount of Co precursor was varied (from 0.1 to 0.9 mmoles), while all the other parameters were held constant. Since the mmole of Fe precursors added are always equal to 1, the Co/Fe feed ratio (bottom axis) is numerically equal to the moles of Co precursor added, and the ratio of surfactants molecules per total metal precursors (top axis) is then equal to $6/(1 + \text{mmoles}_{\text{Co}})$. Grey points and shaded area: syntheses of cobalt ferrite nanocubes in which both the amounts of Co and of Fe precursors added were varied in a way that the surfactant/(total metal) ratio remained around 4. Note that the position of these grey data points in the plot refers to the Co/Fe feed ratio (bottom axis) and to the Co stoichiometry (left axis) and Co/Fe ratio in the particles (right axis), while the surfactant/(total metal) ratio is indicated by the position of the corresponding cube sketches in the shaded area.

Figure 2. TEM images of $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes with cobalt stoichiometry (x) equal to (a) 0.1, (b) 0.4, (c) 0.5, (d) 0.6, (e) 0.8 and (f) 1. Scale bars are 50 nm in all images. Co/Fe feed ratios and surfactant/(total metal) ratios are reported in Table 1. Additional details are found in Table S1 and Figure S2 of the SI.

Table 1. Relevant parameters for the $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ nanocube samples of Figure 2

Panel of Figure 2	Co/Fe feed ratio	Surfactant/ (total metal) ratio	Co/Fe ratio in the NCs	Co stoichiometry (x) in the NCs
A	0.11	5.4	0.03	0.1
B	0.33	4.5	0.15	0.4
C	0.5	4	0.2	0.5
D	0.64	4	0.25	0.6
E	0.74	3.9	0.36	0.8
F	0.84	3.9	0.5	1

Synthesis of nanocubes with fixed Co stoichiometry and tunable size. To synthesize stoichiometric CoFe_2O_4 NCs (that is, with $x=1$) with tunable size, we discovered that we could individually vary two main parameters: i) the heating ramp and ii) the relative ratio of squalane to dibenzyl ether (while keeping the total solvent volume at 25 mL). Tuning the heating ramp was preferred for a fine tuning of the edge size of the cubes in the 15-30 nm size range. For example, by fixing the surfactant/(total metal) ratio to 4 and the Co/Fe feed ratio to 0.88 and by decreasing instead the heating rate from $20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to $5.2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, the size of the nanocubes could be tuned from 15 ± 2 to 27 ± 3 nm, while the stoichiometry of the particles was always equal to CoFe_2O_4 . The detailed ICP data and estimated Co content and compositions are summarized in Table S2 of SI. Representative TEM images of samples prepared under different heating ramps are reported in Figure 3, see also Table 2 (size distribution plots are given in Figure S3 of the SI). Instead, varying the relative proportions of squalane and benzyl ether was preferred for a coarser size tuning of the CoFe_2O_4 nanocubes in the 20-100 nm size range. For example, the size of CoFe_2O_4 nanocubes could be increased from 20 to 85 nm by increasing the volume fraction of squalane from 0.30 to 0.80. Interestingly, when working at 100% squalane, multibranch nanostructures of around 100 nm in size were synthesized, along with cubes of 25 nm with narrow size distributions (see Figure S3 of the SI). It is worth to mention that the stoichiometry of CoFe_2O_4 NCs, with $x=1$ refers to as-synthesized samples in the non-aqueous phase. Upon water transfer, the cobalt content for only CoFe_2O_4 NCs changes from $x=1$ to $x=0.7$, suggesting a partial Co ion leakage from the particles during the transfer (see later).

Figure 3. TEM images of as-synthesized CoFe_2O_4 nanocubes of sizes equal to (a) 15 ± 2 (b) 19 ± 2 (c) 23 ± 2 and (d) 27 ± 3 nm, which were prepared by setting the heating ramp at $20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, $14^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, $7.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, and $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, respectively, while maintaining all the other reaction parameters constant. Scale bars indicate 50 nm in all images. Additional details are found in Table S1 and Figure S3 of the SI.

Table 2. Relevant parameters for the $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ nanocube samples of Figure 3

Panel of Figure 3	Co/Fe feed ratio	Surfactant/ (total metal) ratio	Heating rate ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$)	Co stoichiometry (x) in the NCs	NC size (nm)
<i>a</i>	0.88	4	20	1	15 \pm 2
<i>b</i>	0.88	4	14	1	19 \pm 2
<i>c</i>	0.88	4	7.5	1	23 \pm 2
<i>d</i>	0.88	4	5	1	27 \pm 3

Structural characterization. The recorded X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the as-synthesized NCs matched the bulk pattern of the stoichiometric CoFe_2O_4 spinel ferrite crystal structure (Figure S5, JSPDC card number 22-1086), regardless of Co stoichiometry and size of the NCs. Also, the samples did not contain impurities ascribable to FeO , CoO or Co_3O_4 , as reported instead in previous works on cobalt-substituted magnetite NCs prepared by thermal decomposition.⁴² The only exception in our case was represented by the sample prepared using only squalane (100%) as solvent, which yielded mixtures of cubes and branched structures as mentioned above, and in which the major component was represented by a Wurtzite phase, with the spinel present only as a secondary phase (Fig. S6, SI).

Detailed compositional analysis was then performed by TEM on a 20 \pm 2 nm $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{2.5}\text{O}_4$ nanocube sample and on a 27 \pm 3 nm CoFe_2O_4 nanocube sample. Co stoichiometries equal to 0.5 (\pm 0.1) and 0.8 (\pm 0.3) were estimated by STEM-EDS analyses (Table S3) over large groups of NCs for the 20 nm and the 27 nm samples, respectively, which match the stoichiometries measured by elemental analysis by ICP-OES on NC solutions. The Co and Fe distributions within the NCs were analysed by EF-TEM and by STEM-EDS elemental mapping (Figure 4). For both samples, EF-TEM elemental maps indicated a homogeneous distribution of Fe within the NCs, whereas the distribution of Co was less homogenous and evidenced an enrichment of Co closer to the surface. This result was further confirmed by STEM-EDS line scans along individual cube diagonals, which evidence a modulation of the Fe signal that roughly follows the intensity profile in the HAADF-STEM image (related to the thickness) and a depletion of Co in the central region of the NCs. This gradient in the Co:Fe ratio from the surface to the inner region of the NCs may indicate the formation of different magnetic phases. Although no secondary phases were detected from the XRD pattern, it should be said that a low volume fraction of the Co-rich phase at the NC surface

(which may go unnoticed in XRD) could still significantly affect the magnetic properties. As shown in typical representative EM images (Figure 4a-f), it is also important to highlight that at a Co content around 0.5, the resulting $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{2.5}\text{O}_4$ NCs have a slightly concave cubic shape rather than being more regular cubic shape particles as for other different composition, such as CoFe_2O_4 with cobalt content of 1 (Figure 4g-l). Such control in shape (either close to perfect cube or a slightly concave cube, depending on the Co content) was highly reproducible (see also Figure 2).

Figure 4. Compositional analysis of two cobalt ferrite nanocube samples, i.e. $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{2.5}\text{O}_4$ (left column) and CoFe_2O_4 (right column). (a, g) Zero-loss filtered TEM images of a group of nanocubes in each sample and (b, h) combination of corresponding EF-TEM elemental maps for Fe (red) and Co (green). The Fe and Co maps are shown separately in (d, j) and (f, l) respectively, for the sake of clarity. (c, i) HAADF-STEM images of a single nanocube from each sample and (e, k) profiles of the integrated Fe and Co K α peaks along the diagonal lines drawn in (c, i).

Magnetic characterization. Figure 5 reports the M-H loops recorded on 27 ± 3 nm CoFe_2O_4 and 20 ± 2 nm $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{2.5}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes. At 298 and at 5 K, the M-H loop of the 27 nm

CoFe₂O₄ sample exhibited a hysteresis, with finite coercivity (which is a characteristic feature of ferro- or ferromagnetic NCs), with no deviations at low magnetic fields. An increase in the coercive field at 5 K confirmed the higher magnetic ordering at low temperature. The Co_{0.5}Fe_{2.5}O₄ sample at low temperature was characterized instead by a spring-magnet behaviour (also referred as bi-magnet), with the magnetization suddenly decreasing at low magnetic fields and exhibiting a maximum coercive field (H_c) of 13.4 kOe at 5 K. A similar bi-magnetic behaviour was observed for the other sub-stoichiometric (in Co) samples at 5 K (see Figure S7 of the SI). In general, such bi-magnetic behaviour could be ascribed to various phenomena, such as: i) the presence of two NC populations with different sizes and/or compositions;⁷ ii) strong dipolar interactions between the particles;⁵³ iii) the formation of core-shell structures.⁵⁴ In the present cases, it was evident from combined TEM and XRD analysis that both samples had narrow size distributions, with no other impurity phase, which rules out the possibility of having an important contribution from size or compositional distributions. The observed bi-magnetic behavior in the Co_{0.5}Fe_{2.5}O₄ and other sub-stoichiometric sample could arise from both their core-shell structure of such nanocubes, as confirmed by TEM but also by the dipolar interactions (long chains of nanocubes can be seen on the TEM grid of samples deposited from chloroform solution of nanocubes, see for instance Figure S12). This procedure increases the inter-particle distance, on which dipolar interactions are strongly dependent. As a note, a similar bi-magnetic behaviour was observed by Ammar *et al.* in 5.5 nm size CoFe₂O₄ NCs and in this case it was mostly ascribed to the strong dipolar interactions between the (spherical) particles.⁵³

Figure 5. M - H loops of (a) 27 ± 3 nm size CoFe_2O_4 and (b) 20 ± 2 nm $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{2.5}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes at 298 K (open circles) and 5 K (solid circles), respectively. Insert show the zoomed view at low magnetic fields.

Hysteresis loops with finite coercive fields and temperature dependent magnetization were recorded on the NC samples of various sizes and Co stoichiometries (Figure 5, 6 and Figures S7 and S8 of the SI). Figure 6 reports the trends in the values of H_c and of saturation magnetization (M_s) at 298 and 5 K, as extracted from the hysteresis loops. For the series of samples of 20 nm $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ NCs and with Co stoichiometry x in the range $0.1 \leq x \leq 1$, as the cobalt stoichiometry increased from 0.1 to 0.5, the coercive field H_c increased from 106 Oe to 1130 Oe (the highest value for this series of samples, Figure 6a). Then, as the cobalt stoichiometry increased further to 1, H_c decreased to 515 Oe (Figure 6a). The observed trend in H_c as a function of x , as well as the high value of H_c for a composition around $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{2.5}\text{O}_4$, are both consistent with literature reports.⁴⁹ As a note, Wu *et al.* measured a H_c value of 810 Oe on 20 nm $\text{Co}_{0.6}\text{Fe}_{2.4}\text{O}_4$ NCs at room temperature.³⁰ A similar trend of H_c over x was observed at low temperature (5 K), with the notable difference that the H_c values were higher than the 298 K ones by one order of magnitude. H_c peaked again at $x = 0.5$, reaching 13.4 kOe. Such higher values at 5 K are due to the increased magnetic ordering at low temperature that is typical of ferromagnetic NCs.^{39, 55}

An important parameter that can be extracted from M vs. H hysteresis curves in magnetic materials is their squareness, which is a measure of how the curves deviates from a square, and is defined as the ratio between M_r/M_s with M_r being the remanent magnetization. For the NCs reported here, the highest squareness was observed for $x= 0.5$ at 5 K (0.82), while for the other Co stoichiometries it ranged from 0.74 to 0.79. This is in accordance with previous reports.³⁷ Also, as the cobalt stoichiometry increased from 0.1 to 1, the saturation magnetization M_s decreased systematically from 74 emu/g to 42 emu/g at 298 K and from 87 emu/g to 55 emu/g at 5 K (see Figure 6b). This trend can be rationalized by considering that the Co^{2+} ions, being smaller than the Fe^{2+} ions, tend to occupy both the octahedral sites and the smaller tetrahedral sites. Such mixed occupancy can break the antiferromagnetic ordering among the Fe^{3+} ions that are instead equally distributed among tetrahedral and octahedral sites and can lead to a lower magnetic moment with increasing Co^{2+} content.

In case of NCs with fixed CoFe_2O_4 composition and increasing size, H_c decreased, both at 298 K (from 665 Oe to 400 Oe) and at 5 K (from 9.25 kOe to 7 kOe) as reported in Figure 6c. A systematic decrease in H_c with increasing size suggests that in the range of sizes under study there is at some point a transition from single domain ferrimagnetic to multi domain ferromagnetic behaviour. This is consistent with a previous report on spherical CoFe_2O_4 NCs, which indicated 20 nm as the transition size.^{37, 50} Since the volume of a 20 nm sphere corresponds to a cube with 16 nm edge length, we conclude that 16 nm should be the estimated transition size from single to multidomain in our nanocubes. The trend in M_s over NC size increased, from 47 to 64 emu/g at 298 K and from 56 to 73 emu/g at 5 K and it is in accordance with similar trends reported in literature, where the M_s increases with size and approached the bulk value, see Figure 6d.³⁷ Also, the observed M_s values were lower than their bulk counterpart, and this can be explained by the surface disorder in colloidal NCs (also note that surface disorder is even more pronounced in spherical shape particles than in cubic shaped particles).

Figure 6. Variation of coercive field (H_c) and saturation magnetization (M_s) at 5 K (solid circles) and 298 K (open circles) as a function of (a & b) cobalt content in $Co_xFe_{3-x}O_4$ ($0.1 \leq x \leq 1$) for 20 nm cube-edge nanocrystals and (c & d) different size nanocubes with cobalt content of 1 respectively.

Water transfer of the nanocubes. To study the relaxivity and the heating ability, water transfer of the as-synthesized organic capped NCs was needed. Decanoic acid coated $Co_xFe_{3-x}O_4$ ($0.1 < x < 1$) nanocubes with different sizes and Co stoichiometries were transferred in water by embedding them in an amphiphilic alkyl polyanhydride polymer, using a well-established procedure.^{51, 52} As found by ICP analysis, for the nanocubes $CoFe_2O_4$ NCs with cobalt content $x=1$, the polymer coating was found to significantly reduce the Co content passing to $Co_{0.7}Fe_{2.3}O_4$ after polymer coating. The loss however was remarkable only for samples with high cobalt content and which was instead negligible for cobalt stoichiometries below 0.5. The observed 10 – 30% cobalt loss from the $CoFe_2O_4$ NCs was nevertheless lower than that observed by Schultz-Sikma *et al.* (which was as high as 75% after dialysis on freshly prepared water soluble NCs)¹¹ by us. Once coated by polymer, our NCs remained stable in aqueous solution for several months, without any sign of aggregation, as confirmed

by TEM analysis (See Figure S9 of the SI and by. the average hydrodynamic sizes measured by dynamic light scattering. This was the case for both nanocubes at different Co compositions and fixed size (Figure S10 and Table S4) as well as for samples of different sizes and fixed $\text{Co}_{0.7}\text{Fe}_{2.3}\text{O}_4$ composition (Figure S9).

Temperature dependent magnetization (ZFC and FC) and M-H loops were then measured for two selected polymer coated samples (20 nm $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{2.5}\text{O}_4$ and 27 nm $\text{Co}_{0.7}\text{Fe}_{2.3}\text{O}_4$ NCs). The magnetic measurements indicate that for the 20 nm $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{2.5}\text{O}_4$ after polymer coating, the bi-magnetic behaviour disappears at 5 K (Figure S11). However, the distribution of Fe and Co by EF-TEM mapping did not change before and after the water transfer thus supporting the presence of core-shell also after water solubilisation of nanocubes (Figure SI). .Worthy, also for the sample CoFe_2O_4 , although the leakage of cobalt takes place during water transfer, the characteristic future of $\text{Co}_{0.7}\text{Fe}_{2.3}\text{O}_4$ remains core-shell once in water . Instead for the samples at size of 20 nm but different Co content at 0.3 and 0.7 a more homogeneous distribution of cobalt and iron was observed under TEM thus suggesting the importance of the core-shell structure to have higher R2 values (Figure S14, SI)

We also note that the amphiphilic polymer around each NC reduces the inter-particle dipolar interactions: the polymer coated cubes were still able to arrange in linear chains, although by looking at the TEM images, these chains were shorter than those observed from samples as-synthesized and deposited from the organic solution (Figure S9 and S12). On the other hand, the absence of a proper peak in the ZFC magnetization curve suggests that the spins are blocked up to 400 K. Also, the flatness in the FC magnetization additionally confirms that the extra polymer shell does not completely suppress the interaction between nanocubes.

Relaxivity characterization. The relaxivities of polymer coated nanocube samples of various Co stoichiometries and sizes were then measured (Figure 7 and Figure S14). For 20 nm nanocube size with different Co content, except for $x = 0.5$ case, the r_2 relaxivity values increase in the range between 555 to 615 $\text{mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ at increased Co content. A record value of 958 $\text{mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ at a magnetic field of 0.5 T, is reached for 20 nm $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{2-x}\text{O}_4$ cubes with $x=0.5$ reached (Figure 7a), Exceptionally high r_2 relaxivity for this sample might be due to many reasons including: (i) At 0.5 cobalt content, the EFTEM (Figure S13) confirm the core-shell behaviour with Fe rich center and Co rich ferrite phase at the edges (this was not the case for Co content of $x=0.3$ and 0.7, see figure S14); (ii) SQUID measurements for $x = 0.5$ case

exhibits the highest magnetic moments and coercive fields among the samples at different cobalt content; (iii) this sample differently from all the others has also a slightly different shape, it is not a perfect cube but it has a slightly concave shape. Although no previous work was correlating r_2 relaxivity to different shape of cobalt ferrite nanocrystals, it might be useful to recall that in the case of iron oxide nanocrystals, Zhao et al.⁵⁶ have shown that creating octapod shape have higher relaxivity than spherical shape iron oxide nanocrystals, as the effective radius increased to (r_2 values of $680 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ were measured at a field of 11.7 T so please note that a direct comparison with our results at 1.5 T cannot be straightforward).

Also, according to the theoretical predictions, high r_2 relaxivity values of 1200–1800 $\text{mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ should be achieved in core-shell ($\text{Fe@Fe}_3\text{O}_4$) or in mixed spinel ferrite ($\text{Zn}_{0.4}\text{Fe}_{0.6}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$) NCs.⁴⁴ Therefore, the observed high values might be rationalized based on theoretical predictions of core-shell or mixed spinel structures.⁴⁴ Hence, concave nanocubes with high magnetic moments and coercivity field and at the same time with a core-shell structure could all be the right parameters to combine to provide more magnetic field inhomogeneity around the particles and reach such very high r_2 values.

In the series of samples of fixed compositions and different sizes, the r_2 relaxivity (measured again at 0.5 T) increased from 452 to $725 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ as the size of the $\text{Co}_{0.7}\text{Fe}_{32.3}\text{O}_4$ NCs increased from 15 ± 2 to 27 ± 3 nm. Samples presenting at the same time small hydrodynamic sizes, a narrow size distribution (see Figure S10 and Table S4 of SI) and a high magnetic moment display higher r_2 relaxivity values. Also, as the r_2 relaxivity is directly related to M_s , an increase in r_2 with size is expected. Fast diffusion of single domain magnetic NCs provides rapidly changing magnetic fields for proximal protons, which are time averaged. Therefore, in the motional averaging regime region, the relaxivity of nanoparticles are lower and they are size dependent. For bigger NCs, the diffusion effects become less important and the NCs can be considered as static. In this case, the protons experience a static magnetic field. At this size range, the relaxivity is independent of the size of NCs (more details are found in the SI).⁴⁴

Is worth of note that the r_2 relaxivity values measured by us were generally higher than those reported in the literature. For example, a r_2 relaxivity of $553 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ was reported by Georgiadou *et al.* at an applied magnetic field of 11.7 T for 10 nm size CoFe_2O_4 NCs,⁴⁷ while iron oxide nanocubes of 22 nm edge size, prepared by thermal decomposition, displayed an r_2 value of $760 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, as found by Lee *et al.*¹⁶ Moreover, the r_2 relaxivity values measured on

our particles decreased systematically for all the compositions and sizes with increasing magnetic field (from 0.5 to 1.5 T), which might be explained by considering the increased inter-particle interactions at higher magnetic fields.

Figure 7. r_2 relaxivity of (a) 20 nm $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ ($0.1 \leq x \leq 1$) and (b) different size (15 to 27 nm) $\text{Co}_{0.7}\text{Fe}_{2.3}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes measured at 0.5 T, 1 T and 1.5 T. The insert show the representative TEM images of $x = 0.5$ and 27 nm case. The corresponding scale bar is 50 nm.

SAR measurements. The heating performance of the nanocubes was evaluated by measuring the raise in temperature under an applied AC field (Figure S15). The heating ability of the nanocubes are quantified by estimating the SAR values of $\text{Co}_{0.7}\text{Fe}_{2.3}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes of different sizes (15, 17, 19, 23 and 27 nm) and for 20 nm $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes with different cobalt contents (Figure 8). For the $\text{Co}_{0.7}\text{Fe}_{2.3}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes, the highest SAR values were recorded on the 17 and 19 nm samples. The observed behaviour is consistent with our recent findings on polymer coated iron oxide nanocubes, for which the highest performance was measured on cubes of about 19-20 nm in edge size.⁶ Remarkably, the SAR values recorded at 105 kHz and under the same experimental conditions (hyperthermia set up, volume of sample and concentration, etc.) for the 17–19 nm $\text{Co}_{0.7}\text{Fe}_{2.3}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes prepared in this work are three times higher than those of Fe_3O_4 nanocubes of comparable sizes and described by us in a previous work.⁵⁷ As per our previous report,⁵⁸ gallic PEG ligand was successfully used for the water transfer of large iron oxide nanocubes (35 nm) but this approach did not work for the cobalt ferrite nanocubes studied here. This might be due to the low affinity of the catechol group towards the Co-rich nanocube surface, and different derivatized PEG molecules (*i.e.*

amino-PEG) are under way to be tested for the water transfer of cobalt ferrite nanocubes by ligand exchange protocol.

Figure 8. SAR as a function of (a) $Co_{0.7}Fe_{2.3}O_4$ nanocubes with different size (15 to 27 nm) and (b) 20 ± 2 nm $Co_xFe_{3-x}O_4$ ($0.1\leq x\leq 1$) at 105 kHz and 12, 16, 20, 24 and 32 $kA\cdot m^{-1}$.

For 20 nm $Co_xFe_{3-x}O_4$ nanocubes at different composition, we found that the SAR values increased with increasing cobalt content (Figure 8b). The best heating performances were observed for Co content between 0.5 and 0.7. In particular, at 105 kHz and $32 kA\cdot m^{-1}$, the SAR values increased from 560 ± 20 to 915 ± 10 $W/g_{(Co+Fe)}$ when the Co content increased from 0.3 to 0.7. As discussed above, increasing Co content lead to a decrease in the M_s but at the same time led to an increase in the H_c values, reaching the maximum values at 0.5 and 0.7 Co content. A combination of high H_c and moderate M_s results in 20 nm $Co_xFe_{3-x}O_4$ NCs with $x = 0.7$ as the best heat mediators. Noteworthy, the evolution of SAR was practically independent on the frequency in the range investigated, and indeed a high heating performance was reached already at low frequency (105 kHz) (Figure 9). In this regard, the data suggest that the energy dissipated per cycle at 220 and 300 kHz is lower than that at 105 kHz. Likely an increase in frequency might lead to a smaller opening of the hysteresis cycle, thus decreasing the heating efficiency.¹⁴ Also, note that during an hyperthermia experiment the particle temperature is well above the solution temperature, and consequently the actual coercive field is much different from that measured under static conditions at room temperature. The significant SAR values (from 600 ± 10 to $915 \pm 10 W/g_{(Co+Fe)}$) measured by us at clinical frequency (105 kHz) and at conditions of H-f well below the biological limit of $5\cdot 10^9$ $Am^{-1}s^{-1}$ (Figure S16) represent an important advancement in the field of magnetic

hyperthermia, since similar reported values have been recorded only for $H \cdot f$ values above the biological limit. Given the trend of SAR vs. frequency for the present cobalt ferrite nanocubes, we can anticipate that higher heat performances might be reached when applying even lower frequencies (which unfortunately cannot be probed by our experimental device), while keeping the $H \cdot f$ values below the biological limit.

Figure 9. SAR as a function of magnetic field recorded at three different frequencies (105, 220 and 300 kHz) for nanocube sample of (a) 17 ± 2 nm and $Co_{0.7}Fe_{2.3}O_4$ and for a sample of (b) 20 ± 2 nm and $Co_{0.6}Fe_{2.4}O_4$ respectively.

Conclusions:

In conclusion, we have reported an advanced and robust one-pot heat-up method to synthesize spinel ferrite nanocubes $Co_xFe_{3-x}O_4$ with tunable composition ($0.1 \leq x \leq 1$) and size. For a given size, nanocubes with different Co content could be prepared by adjusting, at the same time, the ratio of cobalt to iron precursors and the ratio of surfactants to total Fe+Co precursors. For a given Co content, the size of the nanocubes could be changed by independently tuning either the heating ramp or the solvent composition (a mixture of squalene and benzyl ether). In all the cases, a spinel Co ferrite phase was found by structural characterization except for nanocubes obtained using only squalene as a solvent. From the structural point of view, at $Co_{0.5}Fe_{2.5}O_4$ composition and 20 nm cube edge size and at $Co_{0.7}Fe_{2.3}O_4$ and 27 nm cube edge size, the particles presented a gradient in Co to Fe ratio, with a Fe rich center and a Co rich surface, while a more homogeneous distribution of Fe and

Co was found for samples of 20 nm $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{2-x}\text{O}_4$ with $x= 0.3$ and 0.7 nanocubes. Once transferred in water, the nanocubes preserved their magnetic and structural properties. Only in the case of Co content equal to 1 (CoFe_2O_4 nanocubes), a Co ion leakage in water was observed, which resulted in a final composition around $\text{Co}_{0.7}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$. The $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{2.5}\text{O}_4$ NCs with 20 ± 2 nm size exhibited high r_2 relaxivity values ($985 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ at 0.5 T magnetic field and 19.95 MHz frequency) which might be ascribed to a combination parameters such as the core-shell structures, the high coercivity and magnetization of saturation and the slightly concave shape of the nanocubes, a peculiarity that was observed only at a Co content of 0.5 . For the same sample, a high SAR value of $915\pm 10 \text{ W/g}_{(\text{Co}+\text{Fe})}$ at low frequency (105 kHz) could be recorded. Such high SAR values were also recorded on NC samples having Co content of 0.6 and 0.7 and at frequencies of clinical relevance. This is an important result, since in principle a reduced dose of NCs can be used in magnetic hyperthermia. Overall, our results identify cobalt ferrite nanocubes of 20 nm in size and 0.5 to 0.7 Co content as promising candidates as heat mediators for *in vivo* hyperthermia applications.

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Supporting Information Available: The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website. Additional data for the characterization of the obtained materials, including dynamic light scattering measurements on water soluble nanocubes, XRD patterns, TEM and EF-TEM images deposited from chloroform and from water, ZFC/FC and M-H characterization of nanocubes as synthesized and in water are reported.

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